

Studies in Organic Fluorine Compounds. Synthesis of Fluorinated Hydrazones, Aryl Esters of *p*-Halogenated Phenols, Fluorinated Hydroxy Ketones and their Thiosemicarbazones and Fluoro-substituted Thiazoles and their Mercury Derivatives as Possible Fungicides

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Twenty four fluorinated hydrazones, seven aryl esters of *p*-halogenated phenols, seven fluorinated hydroxy ketones and their thiosemicarbazones, ten fluorosubstituted thiazoles and their mercury derivatives have been synthesised with a view to study their antifungal activity. Most of the compounds were screened for their antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger*. All of them were found to be antifungal.

A NUMBER of acid hydrazides and hydrazones are known to display antitubercular properties. Hydrazones with an oximino group are of some biological interest by virtue of the presence of $-\text{CONH}-\text{N}=\text{C}-$ group which imparts antiparasitic, fungicidal and bactericidal properties to such compounds¹. Since there is a close morphological relationship between physiology of mycobacteria and fungi, such compounds might also be effective against fungi.

Several halogenated phenyl, and benzyl benzoates are toxic to mites and fungi^{2,3}. Alkyl esters of 3,5-dinitro-4-chlorobenzoic acid have been patented as fungicides⁴. Hydroxyketones are well known as contact insecticides in view of their having a combination of toxic and lipoid soluble groupings in the molecule⁵. Buu-Hoi, Xuong and Lavit⁶ have reported the synthesis of certain fluorohydroxyketones exhibiting biologically interesting properties. A number of fluorohydroxy ketones and their allyl ethers have been prepared by Joshi and Bahel⁷ as pesticides. Attempt has also been made to combine the toxicity of ketone molecule with that of thiosemicarbazide which possesses toxophoric $>\text{N}-\overset{|}{\text{C}}-\text{S}$ grouping.

The fungicidal activity of well known organic sulphur fungicides like tetramethyl thiuran disulphide, substituted thioureas, and thiosemicarbazides is attributed to the presence of $>\text{N}-\overset{|}{\text{C}}-\text{S}$ group. This group is also present in thiazoles and

several substituted compounds of this type have pronounced fungicidal activity. 2-Arylamino-4,5-dimethyl thiazoles have been reported to have pronounced fungicidal activity⁸. 2-Aminothiazoles having various substituents, notably fluorine, have been reported to display significant fungicidal action⁹.

Keeping the above facts in view, a number of fluorinated hydrazones, aryl esters of *p*-halogenated phenols, fluorinated hydroxy ketones and their thiosemicarbazones, fluorosubstituted thiazoles and their mercury derivatives have been synthesised. In view of some of the earlier observations on the mercuration of aromatic amines and phenols it has been presumed that the acetoxy mercuri group entered the vacant para position of the aryl nucleus with respect to the $-\text{NH}$ group. If, however, the para position was blocked, the acetoxy mercuri group entered the ortho position. Most of these compounds were screened for their antifungal activity.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected.

Aryl acid hydrazides: These have been prepared from the aromatic carboxylic esters by the method of Tamayo, Alonso and Madronero¹².

Fluoroketones: These have been prepared by the method of Buu-Hoi and Xunog¹³.

Fluorinated aryl acid hydrazones: These were prepared by following the method of Zimmer, Gross, Gerlach, Fry, Pronay and Schmank¹⁴.

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A methanolic solution of an aldehyde or a ketone (0.01M) was added dropwise, with continuous stirring, to a hot methanolic solution of the acid hydrazide (0.01M). The resulting mixture was refluxed gently for half an hour, when solid crystals separated out. It was cooled, filtered and the solid recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. The hydrazones thus prepared have been listed, along with their relevant data, in Table 1.

Aryl esters of p-halogenated phenols : A mixture of a halogenated phenol (0.01M), an acid chloride (0.01M) and magnesium ribbon (0.2 g) was refluxed in benzene for 2 hr. After cooling benzene was distilled off and the residue taken into ether. The ethereal layer was washed with 1% NaOH solution, water and dried. It was recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. The aryl esters thus prepared are listed, along with their relevant data, in Table 2.

To ascertain their structures the esters have been hydrolysed and the acids obtained characterised by their neutralisation equivalents and melting points.

Fluorinated hydroxyketones : An aryl esters (0.01M) was heated with anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.01M) for 2 hr at 130°. The resulting complex was decomposed with ice cold dilute HCl and the liberated product taken into ether. The ethereal layer was washed with water, 1% sodium carbonate solution, water and then dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Excess ether was distilled off and the product recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. The hydroxyketones thus prepared are listed, along with their relevant data, in Table 3.

Thiosemicarbazones : A solution of an appropriate ketone (0.01M) in ethanol was treated with an ethanolic solution of thiosemicarbazide (0.011M) and the mixture refluxed for 30 min. It was cooled and the thiosemicarbazones separating out recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. The thiosemicarbazones thus prepared are listed, along with their relevant data, in Table 4.

Fluorosubstituted thiazoles : A mixture of a fluoro-ketone (0.01M), iodine (0.01M) and an aryl thiourea (0.02M) was heated on a water bath for 40 hr. The

TABLE 1. FLUORINATED HYDRAZONES

S.No.	Compound	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	%Nitrogen	
					Found	Calcd.
1.+	4-Fluoroacetophenone-2-chlorobenzoylhydrazone	124	82.53	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ClFN ₂	9.54	9.63
2.	2-Fluoro-5-methylacetophenone-2-chlorobenzoyl hydrazone	122	89.88	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ ClFN ₂ O	9.00	9.19
3.	4-Fluoroacetophenone-4-chlorobenzoyl hydrazone	202	76.47	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ClFN ₂ O	9.70	9.63
4.	2-Fluoro-5-methylacetophenone-4-chlorobenzoyl hydrazone	133	67.41	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ ClFN ₂ O	9.27	9.19
5.	4-Fluoroacetophenone-2-nitrobenzoyl hydrazone	197	68.75	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ FN ₂ O ₃	13.82	13.95
6.	4-Fluoroacetophenone-3-nitrobenzoyl hydrazone	195	93.75	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ FN ₂ O ₃	13.77	13.95
7.	2-Fluoro-5-methylacetophenone-3-nitrobenzoyl hydrazone	177	86.20	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ FN ₂ O ₃	13.00	13.33
8.	4-Fluoroacetophenone-benzoyl hydrazone	166	78.94	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ FN ₂ O	10.70	10.85
9.	2-Fluoro-5-methylacetophenone-benzoyl hydrazone	131	75.75	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ FN ₂ O	10.28	10.37
10.	4-Fluoroacetophenone-2-hydroxybenzoyl hydrazone	235	89.88	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ FN ₂ O ₂	10.10	10.29
11.	2-Fluoro-5-methylacetophenone-2-hydroxybenzoyl hydrazone.	261	47.87	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ FN ₂ O ₂	9.65	9.79
12.	4-Fluoroacetophenone-4-hydroxybenzoyl hydrazone	232	67.41	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ FN ₂ O ₂	10.20	10.29
13.	2-Fluoro-5-methylacetophenone-4-hydroxybenzoyl hydrazone.	230	42.55	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ FN ₂ O ₂	9.68	9.79
14.	Formaldehyde-4-fluorobenzoyl hydrazone	234 ^d	90.65	C ₈ H ₇ FN ₂ O	9.97	10.84
15.	Acetaldehyde-4-fluorobenzoyl hydrazone	230 ^d	85.46	C ₉ H ₇ FN ₂ O	15.43	15.55
16.	Vanillin-4-fluorobenzoyl hydrazone	158	80.20	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ FN ₂ O ₃	9.70	9.72
17.	Cyclohexanone-4-fluorobenzoyl hydrazone	237	66.66	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ FN ₂ O	11.87	11.96
18.	Benzaldehyde-4-fluorobenzoyl hydrazone	265	95.54	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ FN ₂ O	11.30	11.57
19.	2-Hydroxybenzaldehyde-4-fluorobenzoyl hydrazone	289	71.85	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ FN ₂ O ₂	10.50	10.85
20.*	4-Fluoroacetophenone-4-fluorobenzoyl hydrazone	206	78.65	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ F ₂ N ₂ O	9.90	10.21
21.	Acetophenone-4-fluorobenzoyl hydrazone	182	84.84	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ FN ₂ O	10.80	10.93
22.	4-Methoxybenzaldehyde-4-fluorobenzoyl hydrazone	222	68.18	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ FN ₂ O ₂	10.01	10.29
23.	Cinnamaldehyde-4-fluorobenzoyl hydrazone	210	63.21	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ FN ₂ O	10.20	10.40
24.	2-Fuoro-5-methylacetophenone-4-benzoyl hydrazone	49	90.90	C ₁₄ H ₁₄ F ₂ N ₂ O	9.68	9.72

N.B. *d* denotes decomposed

- + IR Spectral data 3200 cm⁻¹ Secondary amide N-H
- 1675 cm⁻¹ Secondary -CONH-
- 1575 cm⁻¹ C=N (conjugated cyclic system)
- * IR Spectral data 3250 cm⁻¹ Secondary amide N-H
- 1680 cm⁻¹ Secondary -CONH-
- 1540 cm⁻¹ C=N (conjugated cyclic system).

TABLE 2. ARYL ESTERS OF *p*-HALOGENATED PHENOLS

S.No.	Compound	M.P./B.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	%C		%H	
					Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1 ⁺	4'-Fluorophenyl-4-chlorobenzoate	145	91.5	C ₁₃ H ₈ ClFO ₂	61.96	62.27	3.01	3.19
2.	4'-Fluorophenyl-2-nitrobenzoate	180-185/1-3mm	78.2	C ₁₃ H ₈ FNO ₄	59.24	59.77	2.91	3.06
3.	4'-Fluorophenyl-2-phenylacetate	170-180/5mm	69.3	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ FO ₂	72.82	73.04	4.61	4.78
4.	4'-Fluorophenyl-3-bromobenzoate	119	83.0	C ₁₃ H ₈ BrFO ₂	52.62	52.88	2.59	2.71
5.	4'-Fluorophenyl-4-methylbenzoate	78	71.5	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ FO ₂	72.79	73.04	4.64	4.78
6.	4'-Fluorophenyl-4-nitrobenzoate	187-188	86.0	C ₁₃ H ₈ FNO ₄	59.56	59.77	2.89	3.06
7.	4'-Chlorophenyl-3-fluorobenzoate	67-68	79.0	C ₁₃ H ₈ ClFO ₂	61.93	62.27	2.98	3.19

+ IR Spectral data 1730 cm⁻¹ Aryl-CO-O-

TABLE 3. FLUORINATED HYDROXYKETONES

S.No.	Compound	M.P./B.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	%C		%H	
					Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1.	5-Fluoro-2-hydroxyphenyl-4'-chlorophenyl-K	174	98.5	C ₁₃ H ₈ ClFO ₂	61.86	62.27	2.98	3.19
2.	5-Fluoro-2-hydroxyphenyl-2'-nitrophenyl-K	123	86.3	C ₁₃ H ₈ FNO ₄	59.12	59.77	2.89	3.06
3.	5-Fluoro-2-hydroxyphenyl-benzyl-K	200-205/1-2mm	77.8	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ FO ₂	72.76	73.04	4.45	4.78
4.	5-Fluoro-2-hydroxyphenyl-3'-bromophenyl-K	159-160	91.6	C ₁₃ H ₈ BrFO ₂	52.34	52.88	2.46	2.71
5.	5-Fluoro-2-hydroxyphenyl-4'-methylphenyl-K	89	82.3	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ FO ₂	72.76	73.04	4.52	4.78
6 ⁺	5-Fluoro-2-hydroxyphenyl-4'-nitrophenyl-K	141	93.8	C ₁₃ H ₈ FNO ₄	59.23	59.77	2.84	3.06
7.	5-Chloro-2-hydroxyphenyl-3'-fluorophenyl-K	153	88.9	C ₁₃ H ₈ ClFO ₂	61.81	62.27	2.96	3.29

N.B. K denotes ketone
+ IR spectral data 3500 cm⁻¹ Free OH
1670 cm⁻¹ Aryl C=O

TABLE 4. THIOSEMICARBAZONES

S.No.	Compound	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	%N		%S	
					Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1.	5-Fluoro-2-hydroxyphenyl-4'-chlorophenyl-KT	190	96.2	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ ClFN ₂ O ₂ S	12.67	12.98	9.62	9.89
2.	5-Fluoro-2-hydroxyphenyl-2'-nitrophenyl-KT	178	94.3	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ FN ₂ O ₃ S	16.43	16.76	9.26	9.58
3.	5-Fluoro-2-hydroxyphenyl-benzyl-KT	139	83.9	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ FN ₂ O ₂ S	13.65	13.86	10.18	10.56
4.	5-Fluoro-2-hydroxyphenyl-3'-bromophenyl-KT	188	98.0	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ BrFN ₂ O ₂ S	11.12	11.41	8.24	8.69
5.	5-Fluoro-2-hydroxyphenyl-4'-methylphenyl-KT	130	89.0	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ FN ₂ O ₂ S	13.61	13.86	10.21	10.56
6 ⁺	5-Fluoro-2-hydroxyphenyl-4'-fluorophenyl-KT	177	98.6	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ FN ₂ O ₃ S	16.42	16.76	9.25	9.58
7.	5-Chloro-2-hydroxyphenyl-3'-fluorophenyl-KT	193	93.6	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ ClFN ₂ O ₂ S	12.68	12.98	9.63	9.89

N.B. KT denotes ketonethiosemicarbazone
+ IR spectral data 3500 cm⁻¹ Free OH
1590 cm⁻¹ C=N (conjugated cyclic system)
1185 cm⁻¹ C=S.

reaction product was kept for 48 hr in contact with ether to remove any unreacted ketone. It was then washed several times with sodium thiosulphate

solution to remove the excess iodine. The resulting product was boiled with concentrated NH₄OH to liberate the base which was filtered, washed and

recrystallised from aqueous ethanol. The fluoro-thiazoles thus prepared are listed, alongwith their relevant data, in Table 5.

Mercury derivatives: The fluorosubstituted thiazole (0.01M) was dissolved in the minimum amount of alcohol-acetic acid medium. To this a dilute

acetic acid-water solution of mercuric acetate (0.015M) was added. The resulting mixture was shaken well and kept as such for 24 hr. The separated solid product was filtered, washed successively with water, dilute acetic acid and alcohol. It was collected. The mercury derivatives thus prepared are recorded, along with their relevant data, in Table 6.

TABLE 5. FLUORO-SUBSTITUTED THIAZOLES

S. No.	Compound	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	%S	
					Found	Calcd.
1.	2-Anilino-4-(2'-chloro-5'-fluoro)phenyl thiazole	77	69.3	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ ClFN ₂ S	10.17	10.50
2*	2-Amino-4-(5'-fluoro-2'-methoxy)phenyl thiazole	164	87.8	C ₁₀ H ₈ FN ₂ O ₂ S	13.87	14.28
3†	2-p-Methylanilino-4-(5'-fluoro-2'-methoxy)phenyl thiazole	71-72	83.0	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ FN ₂ O ₂ S	9.79	10.19
4.	2-p-Chloroanilino-4-(2'-fluoro-5'-methyl)phenyl thiazole	119	89.6	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ClFN ₂ S	9.86	10.04
5.	2-o-Chloroanilino-4-(2'-fluoro-5'-methyl)phenyl thiazole	128	92.0	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ClFN ₂ S	9.76	10.04
6.	2-p-Chloroanilino-4-(5'-fluoro-2'-methoxy)phenyl thiazole	138	93.8	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ ClFN ₂ O ₂ S	9.12	9.56
7.	2-o-Methylanilino-4-(5'-fluoro-2'-methoxy)phenyl thiazole	102	79.6	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ FN ₂ O ₂ S	9.82	10.19
8.	2-o-Methoxyanilino-4-(5'-fluoro-2'-methoxy)phenyl thiazole	121	66.8	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ FN ₂ O ₂ S	9.24	9.69
9.	2-p-Methoxyanilino-4-(5'-fluoro-2'-methoxy)phenyl thiazole	89	73.0	C ₁₇ H ₁₅ FN ₂ O ₂ S	9.26	9.69
10.	2-Amino-4-(2'-chloro-5'-fluoro)phenyl thiazole	97-99	74.8	C ₉ H ₈ ClFN ₂ S	13.72	14.00
	* IR spectral data	3270 cm ⁻¹	Secondary N-H			
		2850 cm ⁻¹	-C-O-CH ₃			
		1640 cm ⁻¹	C=N			
		775 cm ⁻¹	-S-			
	+ IR spectral data	3300 cm ⁻¹	NH ₂			
		2800 cm ⁻¹	-C-O-CH ₃			
		1550 cm ⁻¹	C=N			
		745 cm ⁻¹	-S-			

TABLE 6. MERCURY DERIVATIVES OF FLUORO-SUBSTITUTED THIAZOLES

S. No.	Compound	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular formula	%Hg	
					Found	Calcd.
1.	2-{2'-Acetoxymercuri-4'-methyl}anilino-4-{5'-fluoro-2'-methoxy}phenyl thiazole.	188	48.8	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ FN ₂ O ₃ SHg	35.47	35.93
2.	2-{4'-Acetoxymercuri}anilino-4-{2'-chloro-5'-fluoro}phenyl thiazole.	155	73.0	C ₁₇ H ₁₂ ClFN ₂ O ₂ SHg	36.15	36.53
3†	2-{4'-Acetoxymercuri-2'-methyl}anilino-4-{5'-fluoro-2'-methoxy}phenyl thiazole.	165	32.6	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ FN ₂ O ₃ SHg	35.50	35.93
4.	2-{2'-Acetoxymercuri-4'-chloro}anilino-4-{2'-fluoro-5'-methyl}phenyl thiazole.	233	74.0	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ ClFN ₂ O ₂ SHg	35.12	35.66
5.	2-{4'-Acetoxymercuri-2'-chloro}anilino-4-{2'-fluoro-5'-methyl}phenyl thiazole.	Turns black at 189	68.3	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ ClFN ₂ O ₂ SHg	35.16	35.66
6.	2-{2'-Acetoxymercuri-4'-chloro}anilino-4-{5'-fluoro-2'-methoxy}phenyl thiazole.	216	59.0	C ₁₈ H ₁₄ ClFN ₂ O ₃ SHg	34.23	34.65
7.	2-{4'-Acetoxymercuri-2'-methoxy}anilino-4-{5'-fluoro-2'-methoxy}phenyl thiazole.	245 ^d	41.3	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ FN ₂ O ₄ SHg	34.42	34.97
8.	2-{2'-Acetoxymercuri-4'-methoxy}anilino-4-{5'-fluoro-2'-methoxy}phenyl thiazole.	193	56.0	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ FN ₂ O ₄ SHg	34.47	34.97
	N.B. d denotes decomposed					
	+ IR spectral data	3250 cm ⁻¹	secondary N-H			
		2850 cm ⁻¹	-C-O-CH ₃			
		1580 cm ⁻¹	C=N			
		1380 cm ⁻¹	O-CO-CH ₃			
		720 cm ⁻¹	-S-			

Fungicidal Activity

Most of the compounds were screened for their antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger* by agar plate technique^{15,16} at three different concentrations namely 1 : 1,000; 1 : 10,000 and 1 : 100,000.

All the compounds that have been screened were found to be antifungal, Compounds 3, 4, 8, 21, 22 and 23 of Table 1, compounds 3, 4, 5 and 7 of Table 2, compounds 2 and 6 of Table 3, compounds 1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8 and 9 of Table 5 and all the compounds of Table 6 have been found to be most active.

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